

Didactic Means of Formation of Creative Ability in Students

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Abstract. *this article discusses the need to use a divergent type of activity to develop the creative thinking of elementary school students.*

Key words: *education, upbringing, creative thinking, didactics, critical thinking, divergent thinking, convergent thinking.*

A set of didactic tools presented to young students based on the traditional educational process based on imparting knowledge has been expressed. They appear in the form of educational programs, textbooks, training manuals. Educational materials as redeveloped forms of culture are presented to students within the framework of educational subjects. The knowledge, skills and competences provided for in the DTS are expressed within the educational subject. Pupils can form thoughts in relation to material existence. A person develops his thoughts independently, he cannot master them ready-made. Thoughts are formed with the help of aspirations, experiences, emotions, which are formed with the help of productive methods. Also, materials that allow the transfer of information and direct cooperation also help students to form an objective opinion. External requirements that are not based on values and mechanisms of independent thinking do not serve to expand the possibilities of creative thinking of students. Only personal thoughts can help students develop creative skills. Personality formation is a socially dependent process of self-development. It represents the inner striving of the student from a low to a high level of development. In such conditions, external causes move through internal conditions. In the same conditions, the emergence of creative activity is observed in a particular student.

From a psychological point of view, the student's activity is interpreted as his attitude to his work. Activity is a specific state of coordinated actions of students. It appears as an expression of diligence. The student's activity is manifested as his academic work, the speed and enthusiasm he shows in the process of acquiring knowledge. The unique aspect of activity has been revealed by many experts. They are V. A. Petrovsky, A. G. Asmolov, R. Safarova, B. Adizov, G. Najmiddinova, E. Goziev, M. Davletshin. As an activity related to the educational situation, based on the activity that is not adapted within the initial situations, based on indiscriminate, erratic actions, the student not only strives to improve his activity, but also designs new, interesting goals and abandons the previously existing activity style. As part of our research, we will focus on the pedagogical possibilities of directing students' intellectual and creative activities to a specific goal during the educational process. This, in turn, allows students to develop reflection and to search for the logic of the educational process, to direct them to actively act in pedagogical situations aimed at creating reflection content. The theoretical model of the person-oriented pedagogical situation embodies the following:

- the content of activity aimed at a specific goal, this activity embodies the fulfillment of tasks and solutions related to the social and cultural sphere;
- the composition of the students who entered into pedagogical cooperation and the tasks they perform, their real, organizational relations and positions;

- forms and methods of business and interpersonal cooperation;
- personal tasks of students, situations that require them to perform certain tasks in this situation;
- views of situation development;
- driving forces forming the situation;
- inclinations and methods of activity of the participants of the situation.

The same didactic units allow students to properly equip the processes of performing creative tasks. First of all, it is manifested in the information field in the form of personal creative tasks, special relationships and life activities. Second, the person-centered learning situation embodies the development of two trends. The influence of external conditions on the personality of the student, the influence of the way of activity on the personality, is formed in the process of determining his personality, on the one hand, the internal active point of view of the personality of the student, and on the other hand, in the process of self-expression and behavior. Thirdly, in the educational situation, the personality of the teacher and the student meet and enter into cooperation. In this, the purposeful, meaningful, procedural aspects of the educational process arise. In this way, favorable conditions are created for the implementation of a full-fledged didactic process. The goal of the learning situation proposed by the teacher can be recognized as a person-oriented goal. The purpose of the learning situation is such that it does not directly arise from the demand of the situation. Its practical application implies achieving the set goal (V.A.Petrovsky (146, S.91)). Thus, the goal of the learning situation is the specific goal of the learner and the students in the situation. As a result of such an educational situation, in addition to mastering the required knowledge and methods of activity, students will have new opportunities for them. They will have the opportunity to increase their personal experiences, organize their life situations, and change depending on the social environment that surrounds them. Pupils have the potential to set new demands on themselves by being active in solving the tasks envisaged within the framework of the situation. This is reflected in their independence in solving tasks. As a result, they help the manifestation of the acceleration of the student's personality in cognitive activities. The student's cognitive inclinations are based on the above-mentioned cognitive states. It is of particular importance what tasks the student solves in the implementation of his activity. While the desire to know forms its basis, in the processes of solving the essence of these tasks, the student creates his image, performs self-knowledge. This is reflected in his independent aspirations to work. Solving such internal issues will help you realize that you are capable of these tasks. Success in solving problems is also an opportunity for self-expression. It also depends on the student's own requirements. We try to identify 3 stages of cognitive performance: The first stage is an assessment of one's situational capabilities. The student works on the basis of solving the tasks facing such a situation. For this purpose, the student asks the following questions and answers them. Am I ready to accomplish my goals? Am I capable of accomplishing the tasks I have set for myself? In such circumstances, the evaluation of one's own abilities is not always important for the student. The assessment of his situational capabilities may also be of incidental importance to him. The second stage is a self-assessment, in which the student emerges as a specific person with cognitive abilities. In this case, the person's cognitive capabilities cannot be the object of evaluation. It operates as an entity that occupies these opportunities. That is why he tries to accept solutions. In this place, the activity is distinguished by the unique aspects of the person. Unsolved problems, as well as solved ones, appear as an existing sign, which is important in assessing the student's personality. The third stage is an assessment of the student's existing capabilities, parts, and depth. In this process, it is assumed that the student determines his position. When the student solves some educational task, he thinks about the possibilities of solving it and in this process shows his identity. In this situation, the student's attitude towards his work is revealed. The student makes a conclusion about his own knowledge and creative abilities in solving the tasks set before him. The ability to solve the tasks set before him shows the identity of the student.

The formation of reflexive skills in the student takes place in all the above-mentioned stages. In this case: 1) To be able to take the right direction in relation to general relations in the information society, using computer technologies effectively; 2) To master the technology of using a computer during the

educational process, to understand the essence of concepts, to solve problems, to acquire the skills of using information in game and dialogue situations; 3) Accumulation of creative experiences, analysis of valuable capacities, selection of learning methods within educational subjects, having information about the possibilities of ensuring the efficiency of human activity, being able to perceive modern science and technology achievements; 4) Evaluating one's capabilities, determining ways to develop them, having an active personal point of view, looking for ways to activate the educational process, seeing the essence of teaching, getting acquainted with new achievements of the culture of information acquisition. In this process, students' independent learning, self-development, experience of using programmed tools, rational organization of their personal life activities, interests, creative abilities, formation of a responsible attitude to their activities occupy the main place in this process. It is known that students' interests are formed when they have the ability to reflect. This is done in the process of assimilation of information. In this way, the student's interests develop gradually. During the transition from one stage to another, the student begins to solve specific internal tasks. The main essence of these tasks is that the student solves them for the purpose of self-management, self-fulfillment and internal self-affirmation. These tasks differ according to the nature of the initial conditions. According to the type of occurrence of reflexive situations, it is manifested as the student's demands on himself.

In situations where there is a possibility of self-management, two types of experiences are combined: a) concrete-emotional points of view defining his identity are determined; b) vague-emotional doubts, premonitions, expectations, awareness and identification (exactly simile), such simile cannot be carried out within reflexive processes. It is manifested in the process of communication and concrete actions. Exact-emotional experiences depend on traditional conscious states, while ambiguous-emotional experiences occur in unconscious or incomplete states of the learner. Specific emotional experiences are expressed as experiences that serve to understand in similar situations. Ambiguous emotional experiences require an approach within the framework of a person's self-awareness in the direct understanding of processes. The student's demands to solve tasks related to the manifestation of his activity are manifested in the desire to get rid of ambiguous-emotional experiences. And it is carried out by transferring them to the field of concrete-emotional experiences. Thus, the manifestation of one's activity is interpreted in the way of showing one's identity as a separate personal task. It enriches the accuracy in it. The manifestation of individuality is recognized as a characteristic feature of these tasks. When solving problems of application of practical activities, the student works based on the idea of himself and his capabilities. As the student applies his abilities to the activity, he acts within the framework of his ideas and manifests himself in a wide range.

Tasks related to self-affirmation of a person serve as a state of external self-affirmation. In this case, the student strives to be evaluated by those around him according to his maturity. For this, his abilities must be demonstrated in front of the eyes of the people around him. External self-affirmation cannot appear as a task of self-knowledge. In this process, the student acts based on a number of his possibilities. He does not question their similarity and equality and does not seek to change them. Another form of self-affirmation is internal self-affirmation.

According to psychologists, the formation of creative activity is not regular. Its development takes place in two stages. The first stage is expressed in the creative activity of 9-10-year-old students. In this process, students communicate directly with adults. They initially interpret their actions through words. In this place, the speech of students appears as a component of their personal actions. It is at this stage that the first parts of analytical activity are realized in students. This is an initial indicator of analytical activity, which cannot match the analytical activity skills found in 14-16-year-old students.

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